

Synthesis of Coumarins from Phenols and β -Ketonic Esters. Part IV. Coumarins from 4-Chloro- and 2-Nitroresorcins.

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It has been shown by one of us (Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, **8**, 129, 407, 619; 1932, **9**, 25, 31, 389) that phenols which react with difficulty to form coumarins (*e.g.*, phenol, *p*-cresol, halogenated phenols) or do not react at all (*e.g.*, *o*-cresol, nitrophenols, guaiacol, hydroquinone) using sulphuric acid as the condensing agent, yield with phosphorus pentoxide chromones.

It seemed of interest to study the behaviour of negatively substituted resorcinols, pyrogallols, phloroglucinols, naphthols, *p*- and *m*-cresols, which have the faculty of the formation of coumarins with great readiness in Pechmann's reaction in view of the generalisation made by Clayton (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, **93**, 2018) that the presence of a halogen atom in the phenolic nucleus greatly hinders Pechmann's reaction and the presence of a negative substituent like NO_2 or COOH totally inhibits the reaction. The present investigation describes the condensation of chlororesorcin and nitroresorcin with alkylacetoacetic esters both in presence of sulphuric acid and phosphorus pentoxide. It is remarkable that even if there be a halogen atom or any other negative substituent in resorcinol, the reaction takes place smoothly forming substituted coumarins.

Chlororesorcin (b.p. 259° ; m.p. $88.5\text{--}89^\circ$), prepared according to the method of Reinhard (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1878, *ii*, **17**, 336) by the action of sulphuryl chloride on a dry ethereal solution of resorcin, has been proved to be 4-chlororesorcin (Clark, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **55**, 319). It condenses with acetoacetic ester to form 6-chloro-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin. The introduction of the chlorine atom in the molecule of resorcin does not in any way hinder the reaction and the yields of coumarins from 4-chlororesorcin are in some cases higher than the corresponding yields from resorcin.

As chlororesorcin forms coumarins with good yields in presence of sulphuric acid, it also forms coumarins and not chromones by changing the condensing agent for phosphorus pentoxide. Thus the

generalisation made by one of us (Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 31) holds true in this case also.

In order to study the effects of substituents in the acetoacetic ester molecule on the course of the reaction, 4-chlororesorcin has been condensed with different substituted acetoacetic esters *e.g.*, methylacetoacetic ester, ethylacetoacetic ester, propylacetoacetic ester, isobutylacetoacetic ester, benzylacetoacetic ester, α -chloroacetoacetic ester) and also with acetone dicarboxylic acid, aceto-succinic ester and benzoylacetic ester. These condense most readily with good yields forming coumarins in presence of sulphuric acid and even in presence of phosphorus pentoxide, as is proved by their mixed melting points and also by the identity of their derivatives. Thus it is found that a substituent in the acetoacetic ester molecule, however heavy or complex, does not in any way favour the formation of a chromone even in presence of phosphorus pentoxide contrary to the observations of Jacobson and Ghosh (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 424). Incidentally it may also be mentioned that 4-chlororesorcin condenses with malic acid in presence of sulphuric acid to form 6-chloroumbelliferone in good yield just as resorcin produces under these conditions umbelliferone.

2-Nitroresorcin, prepared according to the method of Kauffmann and Pay (*Ber.*, 1904, 37, 716) condenses with acetoacetic ester and methylacetoacetic ester to form coumarins (*e.g.*, 8-nitro-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin and 8-nitro-7-hydroxy-3:4-dimethylcoumarin respectively). It has, however, not been possible to isolate any product using phosphorus pentoxide as the condensing agent due to the formation of resinous products.

The introduction of a substituent in the acetoacetic ester molecule diminishes the yield of coumarin from 2-nitroresorcin and finally retards the reaction as shown below:

	Products.	Yield.
2-Nitroresorcin and acetoacetic ester	8-Nitro-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin	60%
2-Nitroresorcin and methylacetoacetic ester	8-Nitro-7-hydroxy-3:4-dimethylcoumarin	15
2-Nitroresorcin and ethyl-, propyl- or isopropyl-acetoacetic ester	No product isolated.	—

It is well known that umbelliferones exhibit violet fluorescence in alkaline solution. The chloroumbelliferones, described in this

paper, exhibit much stronger fluorescence (bluish violet) than umbelliferones, the fluorescence being appreciably increased with the introduction of heavier substituents in the pyrone ring. The fluorescence of umbelliferones is, however, completely destroyed by the presence of the nitro group.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Coumarins from 4-Chlororesorcin.

6-Chloro-7-hydroxycoumarin.—Chlororesorcin (4.5 g.) and malic acid (5 g.) were intimately mixed and heated carefully on a wire-gauge with double their weight of concentrated sulphuric acid (d 1.84); the mixture began to froth up in a few minutes and eventually appeared as it were to solidify. Heating was continued until the liquid became clear. After cooling the solution was poured into water and the solid crystallised from glacial acetic acid as light ash-coloured needles or prisms, m.p. 271° , yield 1.5 g. It can be further purified by sublimation, when it is obtained as colourless prisms. It exhibits fluorescence in alkaline solution. (Found: Cl, 18.7. $C_9H_5O_3Cl$ requires Cl, 18.06 per cent).

The *acetyl* derivative, prepared by heating with acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate, crystallised from dilute alcohol as colourless prisms, m.p. 166° . (Found: Cl, 14.7. $C_{11}H_7O_4Cl$ requires Cl, 14.85 per cent).

6-Chloro-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin.—To a mixture of 4-chlororesorcin (4 g.) and acetoacetic ester (5 g.), cooled in ice, concentrated sulphuric acid (d 1.84, 10 c.c.) was slowly added with continuous shaking. The solution was kept overnight and poured into ice, when greenish solid separated. It was filtered and crystallised from glacial acetic acid (charcoal) as colourless prisms, m.p. 280° , yield 1.5 g. (Found: Cl, 16.03. $C_{10}H_7O_3Cl$ requires Cl, 16.8 per cent).

The *acetyl* derivative, prepared as usual by heating with acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate, crystallised from dilute alcohol as colourless needles, m.p. 168° . (Found: Cl, 13.82. $C_{12}H_9O_4Cl$ requires Cl, 14.05 per cent).

The identical compound was obtained by using phosphorus pentoxide as the condensing agent. A mixture of 4-chlororesorcin (5 g.) and acetoacetic ester (5 g.) was heated on a boiling water-bath with phosphorus pentoxide (20 g.). After half an hour further amount of phosphorus pentoxide (20 g.) was again added and heating continued for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The mass was then cooled and treated with powdered

ice. The solid which separated was filtered and crystallised from glacial acetic acid (charcoal). The compound was found identical with that prepared by using concentrated sulphuric acid as condensing agent, m. p. 280°, mixed m. p. 280°.

The *acetyl* derivative, prepared in the usual way, melted at 168°, the m. p. being not depressed when mixed with the acetyl derivative of the compound prepared above using sulphuric acid.

The other compounds prepared are described in the table.

Coumarins from 2-Nitroresorcin.

8-Nitro-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin.—To a well-cooled mixture of 2-nitroresorcin (4 g.) and acetoacetic ester (5 c. c.) in a conical flask concentrated sulphuric acid (*d* 1.84, 8 c.c.) was gradually added. The solution was kept overnight and poured into ice, when yellow needles separated. These were filtered, washed with water and crystallised from glacial acetic acid as yellow needles, m. p. 256° (decomp.). It is found to be identical with 8-nitro-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin, prepared by Pechmann and Cohen (*Ber.*, 1901, **34**, 666) by nitrating β -methylumbelliferone, mixed m. p. 256° (decomp.). (Found: N, 6.4. Calc. for $C_{10}H_7O_5N$: N, 6.3 per cent).

The *acetyl* derivative, prepared by heating the substance with acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate, crystallised from glacial acetic acid as yellow prisms, m. p. 198°.

The melting point of the acetyl derivative of Pechmann and Cohen's 8-nitro-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin is recorded to be 165°. The compound, prepared according to Pechmann and Cohen (*loc. cit.*), was also acetylated with acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate and it also melted at 198° and not at 165° as recorded by them. The acetyl derivative (m. p. 198°) has been deacetylated by hydrolysing with 20 % sulphuric acid and crystallised from glacial acetic acid, the deacetylated product melting at 256°.

8-Nitro-7-hydroxy-3:4-dimethylcoumarin.—2-Nitroresorcin was condensed with methylacetoacetic ester in presence of concentrated sulphuric acid in the usual manner, It was crystallised from glacial acetic acid in yellow needles, m. p. 260° (decomp.). (Found: N, 6.7. $C_{11}H_9O_5N$ requires N, 6.4 per cent).

The acetyl derivative, prepared in the usual manner, crystallised from glacial acetic acid as yellow prisms, m.p. 246°. (Found: N, 5.47. $C_{13}H_{11}O_6N$ requires N, 5.1 per cent).

Name and formula.	Prepared from 4-chlororesorcin and	M. p.	Analysis.		Remarks.
			Found.	Req.	
6-Chloro-7-hydroxy-3:4-dimethylcoumarin (C ₁₁ H ₉ O ₃ Cl)	Methylacetoacetic ester (using H ₂ SO ₄ or P ₂ O ₅).	248°	Cl, 14.78	15.3%	Colourless needles from glacial acetic acid.
The acetyl derivative (C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₄ Cl)	...	170°-71°	12.84	13.3	Silky needles from dilute alcohol.
6-Chloro-7-hydroxy-4-methyl-3-ethylcoumarin (C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₃ Cl)	Ethylacetoacetic ester (using H ₂ SO ₄ or P ₂ O ₅).	257-58°	14.91	14.9	Colourless needles from glacial acetic acid.
The acetyl derivative	...	145°	Colourless needles from dilute alcohol.
6-Chloro-7-hydroxy-4-methyl-3-propylcoumarin (C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₃ Cl)	Propylacetoacetic ester (using H ₂ SO ₄ or P ₂ C ₅).	230°	13.57	14.0	Yellow needles from glacial acetic acid.
The acetyl derivative (C ₁₅ H ₁₅ O ₄ Cl)	...	135°	11.91	12.0	Light yellow needles from dilute alcohol.
6-Chloro-7-hydroxy-4-methyl-3- <i>iso</i> butylcoumarin (C ₁₄ H ₁₅ O ₃ Cl)	<i>iso</i> Butylacetoacetic ester (using H ₂ SO ₄).	199°	12.73	13.3	Colourless needles from glacial acetic acid.
6-Chloro-7-hydroxy-4-methyl-3-benzylcoumarin (C ₁₇ H ₁₃ O ₃ Cl)	Benzylacetoacetic ester (using H ₂ SO ₄).	249°	11.91	11.64	Light yellow needles from glacial acetic acid.
3:6-Dichloro-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (C ₁₀ H ₆ O ₃ Cl ₂)	<i>o</i> -Chloroacetoacetic ester (using H ₂ SO ₄ or P ₂ O ₅).	254°	28.48	28.1	Crystallised from dilute alcohol. It exhibits bluish-green fluorescence.
The acetyl derivative (C ₁₂ H ₈ O ₄ Cl ₂)	...	192°	24.82	24.73	Shining needles from dilute alcohol.
6-Chloro-7-hydroxy-coumarin-4-acetic acid (C ₁₁ H ₇ O ₅ Cl)	Acetone dicarboxylic acid (using H ₂ SO ₄).	210°	13.45	13.9	Needles from dilute alcohol. Purified by dissolving in N/10-Na ₂ CO ₃ and acidification.
6-Chloro-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-3-acetic ester (C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₅ Cl)	Ethyl aceto-succinate (using H ₂ SO ₄).	174°	10.92	11.9	Crystallised from dilute alcohol.
6-Chloro-7-hydroxy-4-phenylcoumarin (C ₁₆ H ₉ O ₃ Cl)	Benzoylacetic ester (using H ₂ SO ₄).	258-260°	12.26	13.01	Colourless needles from glacial acetic acid.

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